

Robust packaging for fiber-to-grating couplers in a scalable photonics process

Jeffrey M. Shainline¹, Cale M. Gentry², Sonia M. Buckley¹, Nima Nader¹, Sae Woo Nam¹,
and Richard P. Mirin¹

¹National Institute of Standards and Technology, 325 Broadway, Boulder, CO, 80305, USA

²Department of Electrical, Computer, and Energy Engineering, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, 80309, USA
jeffrey.shainline@nist.gov

Abstract: We present a photonics process utilizing i-line lithography to achieve 2.5 dB/cm losses in low-temperature-deposited SiN. Lithographically-defined fiber packaging structures are aligned to gratings, enabling compact, durable packaging of multiple fibers on a chip and tolerant of temperatures from 1K to 433K.

1. Fabrication and packaging

For integrated-photonics systems to be ubiquitous in the marketplace as well as in laboratory settings, processing must be simple and affordable. Waveguiding devices must interface with sources, detectors and the environment. Optical fibers are the preferred means to achieve this I/O [1]. We present an integrated photonics platform that meets these requirements and is suitable for back-end-of-line incorporation with existing CMOS processing [2], integration with custom fabrication including with low-temperature processes, or as a stand-alone photonics platform.

The waveguiding SiN layer is deposited on thermal oxide using PECVD at 60 °C. We have grown SiN films as thick as 900 nm with no cracking or delamination, but in the present work we have utilized a 220 nm device layer. The devices are patterned using 365 nm i-line stepper photolithography. A 2 μm SiO₂ cladding layer is deposited, also at low-temperature. Finally, fiber support structures are patterned above grating couplers. These fiber support structures comprise two layers of SU-8 epoxy-based photoresist which is permanent upon exposure and curing.

A schematic of the SU-8 packaging is shown in Fig. 1(a). The first layer is referred to as the pedestal; it keeps the fiber oriented at the designed angle relative to the grating. The second SU-8 layer is referred to as the collar, and it serves to align the fiber. In addition to aligning the fiber to the grating, this structure provides a receptacle in which epoxy can be delivered. The low viscosity of the epoxy enables it to run through the channel into the ellipse housing the fiber. Upon filling the entire volume, the epoxy is UV-cured. After placing all fibers, an additional amount of epoxy can be delivered to further strengthen the assembly, as seen in Fig. 1(c,d).

Fig. 1. Fiber packaging scheme. (a) Schematic of fiber in SU-8 collar. (b) Microscope image of two fiber collars aligned above gratings with a ring-bus device. (c,d) Images of packaged chip with four fibers coupled to waveguide devices.

This packaging approach has several strengths. First, the simplicity renders it useful in many contexts. Second, alignment is achieved lithographically. Third, fiber couplers can be placed anywhere on the die for higher density, not just the periphery, as in v-groove-based approaches [1]. Fourth, packaging can be highly automated as the placement of a fiber in a collar and the epoxy delivery is well-suited to robotics with machine vision. And fifth, it is

suitable for a wide range of operating temperatures. With Dymax OP-4-20632 cryogenic epoxy, we demonstrated cooling of a packaged sample down to < 1K, and with Norland Optical Adhesive, we demonstrated heating up to 160 °C.

2. Devices and experimental data

To illustrate the utility of this process, we demonstrated several devices. In Fig. 2(a) we show the response of a ring resonator coupled to a waveguide between two grating couplers. The insertion loss due to the gratings is 6.8 dB/coupler, in close agreement with the simulated value of 6.68 dB/coupler. The 3 dB-bandwidth of this coupler is 90 nm. This spectrum was taken after the fibers were fixed in place using the method described in Sec. 1. Such packaged chips have been observed to maintain stable coupling for weeks, and the fully encased fibers are protected from the environment to enable exceptional longevity. Figure 2(b) shows a microscope image of a fabricated grating coupler before fiber packaging. Figure 2(c) shows a fit to a resonance with Q -factor of 125,000, corresponding to 2.5 dB/cm propagation loss. Figure 2(d) shows a microscope image of the ring-bus coupling gap of a critically coupled ring. This gap is ~ 400 nm, and the critically coupled transmission spectrum is shown in Fig. 2(e). This is the transmission spectrum of four rings coupled to a single bus; one such ring is shown in the inset. Each of the four rings has a slightly different gap, and the optimally coupled device achieved > 25 dB extinction across several FSRs. Finally, we show the spectrum of an unbalanced Mach-Zehnder interferometer demonstrating > 25 dB extinction between all ports across > 40 nm of spectral bandwidth. This extinction demonstrates that the beam splitters created in our process are nearly ideal 50/50 and that the longer arm suffers minimal additional loss.

To demonstrate the stability of the packaging, experiments at low and high temperature have been conducted. The low temperature sample initially had 17 dB insertion loss at room temperature, and upon cooling to 800 mK, this insertion loss increased to 20 dB. This sample has survived two cooling and warming cycles, and more have not been attempted. The high temperature sample initially had 13.7 dB insertion loss. Upon heating to 120 °C, this increased ~ 1 dB. The sample was held at 120 °C for 16 hours with no additional insertion loss. It was then raised to 160 °C, incurring an additional ~ 1 dB insertion loss.

Fig. 2. Photonic device performance. (a) Grating response. (b) Microscope image of grating. (c) High- Q resonance. (d) Ring-bus coupler. (e) Critically coupled rings. (f) Unbalanced Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

4. Conclusions

We have demonstrated a highly scalable integrated photonics platform based on low-temperature-deposited SiN patterned entirely with i-line photolithography using the equipment from a 365 nm technology node. We have introduced a fiber-packaging scheme that utilizes photolithographic alignment in the process flow to pattern fiber support structures above grating couplers, and we have shown that this alignment scheme enables coupling with minimal additional loss as compared to the simulated value.

5. References

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